

Employment

What are the challenges young people face?

Young people feel the current **education system does not prepare them** for their future; It is based on old methodologies and topics and not focused on the skills they will need.

They feel they have a **lack of access to information about the labour market** and how it will change in future. As a result, they struggle to identify which workfields they can or should orientate towards. They do not have sufficient information to decide what skills they will need for this future, and sometimes feel insecure. This means they do not feel prepared for future labour market and how it will develop, particularly with the rise of robotisation.

Young people are also concerned about **employment rights** and things such as, low wages, lack of sick leave, short term and zero hours contracts and unpaid internships.

Some young people face **discrimination in the labour market and workplace**. For example, some young migrants, young Roma and LGBTQI+ young people feel discriminated against when applying for work. Some young people with disabilities cannot access work and find it stressful and exhausting to do so. One working group identified while young people from a higher socioeconomic status placed the emphasis on choosing the right workfield and receiving a satisfying salary, lower-status-participants prioritised simply finding employment.

What is young people's vision for the future?

Young people want to finish education with **suitable skills for the future labour market**. This includes, communication and language skills, leadership and entrepreneurship and digital and technological literacy. It was said to be important to learn how to be flexible and manage your own learning, making changes to a new career when needed.

Young people want the **education system to be linked to the labour market** and modernisation overall. Gaining more practical experience of working whilst studying and having direct links to employers is important. They want **good access to information** on the labour market and job opportunities as well as better recognition of non-formal or informal learning.

Young people want to be more **aware of the worker's rights**, and have better **support from employers for marginalised young people**.

What solutions did young people propose in the consultation?

Young people in the consultation proposed:

- Measures to promote **access to information on the labour market**. Such as access to careers centres, information in schools and online, a European database of jobs, specialist advice and counselling on career choices, and information directly from companies.
- Measures to promote **practical experience of work**, such as paid internships, short and long term volunteering, traineeships, part time jobs whilst studying, opportunities to meet with employers and access to mentors.
- **Reform of the formal educational curriculum**, to focus on more relevant practical competencies and skills, provide better training for specific jobs, and more vocational opportunities.
- **Reform of the educational system and structures**. Such as through closer cooperation between formal education and employers, greater integration of educational systems across Europe, more investment in youth organisations and closer links between formal and non-formal education.

The Survey Data

How important is this issue to young people?

This issue ranks ninth among the priorities, as rated by the young people. It has been measured by one separate item.

What are the priorities for young people?

The answers shown in the graph below indicate, that the young people expect a wide variety of support mechanisms in order to get ready for future working environment and labour market needs. What young people seem to stress are practical opportunities to get hands-on experience, such as training on the job, working while studying, internships, or support in employment-related matters at schools.

Graph below shows that most of the young people consider all of these support mechanisms either somewhat important, or very important.

Graph: The most important support mechanisms in the area of work preparation for young people; percentages.

Where does this report come from?

This report is based on working group and survey responses to consultation question ‘*What can prepare young people for the forms of work that are likely to exist in the future?*’. This question was developed from harvesting tools submitted at the first conference.